

Supplementary Table 1. Post-hoc Tukey test results for MDH levels

MDA	Control	IR	IRr	IRu	IRc
Control	-	<0.001*	0.769	0.232	0.763
IR	<0.001*	-	0.002*	0.021*	<0.001*
IRr	0.769	0.002*	-	0.868	0.158
IRu	0.232	0.021*	0.868	-	0.019*
IRc	0.763	<0.001*	0.158	0.019*	-

* Statistically significant

Supplementary Table 2. Post-hoc Tukey test results for GSH levels

GSH	Control	IR	IRr	IRu	IRc
Control	-	0.001*	0.757	0.679	0.994
IR	0.001*	-	0.030*	0.041*	<0.001*
IRr	0.757	0.030*	-	1.000	0.507
IRu	0.679	0.041*	1.000	-	0.428
IRc	0.994	<0.001*	0.507	0.428	-

* Statistically significant

Supplementary Table 3. Post-hoc Tukey test results for SOD levels

SOD	Control	IR	IRr	IRu	IRc
Control	-	<0.001*	0.060	0.011*	0.999
IR	<0.001*	-	0.002*	0.015*	<0.001*
IRr	0.060	0.002*	-	0.954	0.036*
IRu	0.011*	0.015*	0.954	-	0.006*
IRc	0.999	<0.001*	0.036*	0.006*	-

* Statistically significant

Supplementary Table 4. Post-hoc Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction results for Caspase 3 density

Caspase 3	Control	IR	IRr	IRu	IRc
Control	-	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	1.000
IR	<0.001*	-	0.007*	0.168	<0.001*
IRr	<0.001*	0.007*	-	0.170	<0.001*
IRu	<0.001*	0.168	0.170	-	<0.001*
IRc	1.000	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	-

* Statistically significant

Supplementary Table 5. Post-hoc Tukey test results for Bcl-2 density

Bcl-2	Control	IR	IRr	IRu	IRc
Control	-	<0.001*	1.000	0.378	0.025*
IR	<0.001*	-	<0.001*	0.113	<0.001*
IRr	1.000	<0.001*	-	0.352	0.029*
IRu	0.378	0.113	0.352	-	<0.001*
IRc	0.025*	<0.001*	0.029*	<0.001*	-

* Statistically significant

Supplementary Table 6. Post-hoc Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction results for TNF- α density

TNF- α	Control	IR	IRr	IRu	IRc
Control	-	<0.001*	0.175	0.001*	1.000
IR	<0.001*	-	<0.001*	0.012*	<0.001*
IRr	0.175	<0.001*	-	0.539	0.655
IRu	0.001*	0.012*	0.539	-	0.012*
IRc	1.000	<0.001*	0.655	0.012*	-

* Statistically significant